

Cardiovascular Emergency, Future Direction

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Abstract

Cardiovascular diseases are the top disease killer worldwide. Cardiovascular emergency is one of commonest diseases admitted in emergency treatments in the clinic. A number of factors are associated with therapeutic outcomes for complicate disease conditions. This editorial highlights current and future cardiovascular emergency therapeutics—including emergency rating, diagnosis, anesthesia, surgery and other treatments.

Keywords

Heart Disease Brain Stroke; Cardiovascular Diseases; Diagnosis; Drug Treatments; Emergency Treatment

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases are the top disease killer worldwide caused by different damaging factors, such as smoke, diet, physical inactivity and metabolic diseases [1]. Cardiovascular emergency is one of commonest diseases admitted in emergency treatments in the clinic. A number of factors are associated with therapeutic outcomes for complicate disease conditions [2-4].

Methods

Several important factors are associated with therapeutic outcomes for cardiovascular diseases for emergency cares.

- 1) Quick deaths of patients if a small length of treatment delay;
- 2) Opposite pathways and cascades in pathological progresses (ischemic or breeding);
- 3) Diagnosis and treatments are required as early as possible;
- 4) Excellent for therapeutic choices;

Results

To improve therapeutic outcomes and other economic considerations, several factors may be considered;

- Emergency rating (U/S data) may be gradually perfecting [5]; Comparison between human wisdom (doctor's decision) and digital tools (artificial intelligence AI)
- Diagnosis innovation; (quicker, simpler, cheaper and clearer) quick disease diagnosis can greatly save human life. These kinds of technology are indispensable.
- Pathological knowledge enrichment (basic, experimental and clinical);
- Treatment options from normal surgery and anesthesia in a smaller scales;
- Development of more effective drugs [6];
- Herbal medicine [7], such as she-xiang-bao-xin-wan 麝香保心丸
- High quality nursing [8]

Future Direction

Modern instruments will be utilized for diagnostic improvements and therapeutic options (quick disease localization and therapeutic options-drug or surgery). This needs to update emergency rating and diagnosis.

Pathological knowledge enrichment for cardiovascular diseases and mortality is a future challenge, which may make a diagnostic and therapeutic difference in emergency

Article Information

DOI: 10.31021/ijcmc.20203135

Article Type: Review

Journal Type: Open Access

Volume: 3 Issue: 3

Manuscript ID: IJCMC-3-135

Publisher: Boffin Access Limited

Received Date: 11 January 2020

Accepted Date: 20 January 2020

Published Date: 22 January 2020

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Citation: Da-Yong Lu, Shen Y, Xu B. Cardiovascular Emergency, Future Direction. Int J Clin Med Cases. 2020 Jan;3(3):135

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treatments of both therapeutic types and modern techniques.

Doctors with medical surgery and cardiovascular must be more recruited in emergency medical centers.

Conclusion

Cardiovascular emergency is sudden and pathological diversity. In order to save more lives, diseases pathology and treatment study is required. The final therapeutic outcomes depend on knowledge updating and technical innovation. In addition, creative ideas must be promoted.

References

1. Chakrapani HS, Fulmali MR. Cardiovascular diseases and health. *EC Cardiology*. 2020; 7(2):1-8.
2. Lu DY, Shen Y, Xu B. Heart and brain stroke, a paramount task for emergency medication. *EC Emergency Medicine and Critical Care*. 2019; 3(10):785.
3. Lu DY, Shen Y, Xu b. Brain stroke treatment, emergency importance. *EC Emergency Medicine & Critical Care*. 2019; 3(11):115-117.
4. Khan M, Silver B. Editorial: Stroke in elderly: current status and future direction. *Frontier in Neurology*. 2019; 10:177.
5. Shibl W. The great value of brain U/S in diagnosis of almost all cause of central coma [COMA Protocol]. *EC Emergency Medicine and Critical Care*. 2020; 4(1):1-9.
6. Lu DY, Shen Y, Xu B. Brain stroke, emergency management and drug developments. *EC Pharmacology Toxicology*, 2019; 7(11):1.
7. Lu DY, Lu TR. Herbal medicine in new era. *Hospice Palliative Medicine International J*. 2019;3(4):125-130.
8. Lu DY, Chen YZ, Lu DF, Che JY. Patient's care and nursery in different diseases. *Hospice & Palliative Medicine International Journal*. 2019; 3(1):28-30.